

Petri dishes containing oatmeal agar were inoculated with two standard isolates of the same mating type and one of the rice isolates. After 3-5 d of growth, they were placed under fluorescent light at 20 ± 1 °C. After 3-4 wk, plates were

observed for perithecia formation. Among the 73 isolates tested, 46.6% are Mat 1-1 and 20.5% are Mat 1-2. Nearly 33% of the isolates mated with neither Mat 1-1 nor Mat 1-2.

The results show that both mating-

type isolates are prevalent in Bangladesh. Mat 1-1, however, appears to predominate. We are studying the distribution of the mating types by region and identifying isolates that do not mate with either type. ■

Forecasting rice tungro disease (RTD) occurrence in asynchronous rice planting areas on an empirical basis

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The most frequent and serious outbreaks of RTD during the past decade in Indonesia have occurred in Bali Province, where rice is cultivated asynchronously throughout the year. RTD occurrence fluctuates seasonally in Bali and in the country's other asynchronous rice planting areas. The infected area increases around the start of the wet season (WS), reaches its peak in the mid-wet to early dry season (DS), and shrinks toward the late DS. We studied empirical

1. Regression of RTD-infected area in Oct-Dec on that in Jul-Sep in 3 regencies of Bali, Indonesia, 1983-91. Total area planted to rice in Oct-Dec averaged 24,400 ha.

rules of RTD occurrence in WS in Badung, Tabanan, and Gianyar, the major RTD-endemic regencies of Bali.

Analyses were made with data from Apr 1983 to Mar 1991. Data on monthly rainfall and RTD-infected area were obtained from pest observers' reports. The Bali Provincial Agriculture Service provided relevant agriculture statistics. In Badung, Tabanan, and Gianyar, rice was cultivated in WS on an average of 19,300, 29,800, and 16,000 ha, respectively, and in DS on 16,700, 21,900, and 16,600 ha during the 8-year period.

The RTD-infected area in Oct-Dec (transition to early WS) is positively related with that in Jul-Sep (second half of the DS) when RTD incidence is lowest in a year (Fig. 1). Rainfall, mean temperature, and the area planted with

vector-susceptible cultivars failed to account for significant additional variance in the infected area in Oct-Dec.

The RTD onset month (defined as the month when the newly infected area was greater than twice that of the previous month and increased more than 1 ha) tended to precede the start of WS (monthly rainfall > 200 mm) in years of severe occurrence where infected area in WS was 100 ha. In ordinary years, RTD onset month often came after the beginning of WS (Fig. 2). The difference in RTD onset month relative to that of the WS between the two categories of years is significant (Mann-Whitney U-test, $p < 0.05$).

RTD occurrence in Bali in the 1990-91 WS was successfully forecast using these empirical rules. ■

A procedure for miniscale preparation of *Pyricularia grisea* DNA

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DNA from the blast (BI) pathogen *Pyricularia grisea* can be prepared inexpensively in 1.5-ml microcentrifuge tubes in sufficient quantities for several

Southern hybridizations and polymerase chain reaction experiments. We found that the potassium acetate extraction method can be successfully applied to ground mycelia. The isolated DNA is sufficiently pure to allow digestion with restriction enzymes, making organic solvent extraction optional. Using the following method, DNA can be conveniently extracted from 100 samples

2. Relationship in the starting months between RTD onset (solid circles) and WS (open circles) in 3 regencies of Bali. Stars denote WS of severe RTD occurrence.

of ground mycelia within a day. The procedure is outlined below.

Grow hyphal cultures in 50 ml of Fries medium in 125-ml flasks at 30 °C with shaking. After 5-10 d, harvest the mycelia by suction and lyophilize them. Grind the dried mycelia finely using a mortar and pestle with liquid N or, alternatively, with a few grains of sterile acid-washed sand. If stored at -20 °C with a desiccant, the mycelial powder will keep for several months.

For a single extraction, suspend 50-75 mg of pulverized mycelia in 750 µl extraction buffer (100 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8; 100 mM EDTA; and 250 mM NaCl) by light vortexing in a 1.5-ml microcentrifuge tube. The needed amount of mycelia powder will fill about a quarter of the tube. Add 75 µl 10% (wt/vol) SDS; mix the contents gently and incubate for at least 30 min at 65 °C. Then add 300 µl potassium acetate solution (3 M potassium acetate-2 M acetic acid, pH 4.8), mix gently by inversion, and incubate the tube on ice for 15 min. Spin down precipitate (proteins and detergent) and debris at 13,000 rpm for 15 min.

Carefully transfer 750 µl of supernatant to a fresh tube containing 750 µl 2-propanol. (If a cleaner preparation is needed, the supernatant may be extracted with an equal volume of 24:1 (vol/vol) chloroform-isoamyl alcohol prior to alcohol precipitation.) Invert the tube to mix. Keep the tube on ice for 10 min, or longer if precipitation of nucleic acids is not satisfactory. Pellet down the nucleic acid (13,000 rpm for 5 min), wash with 70% ethanol, air-dry, and resuspend in 40 µl of TE buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.5-8; and 1 mM EDTA). This procedure will yield about 15 µg of DNA.

For a single Southern hybridization, use 1-3 µg of DNA per lane. DNA stored at 4 °C or lower will remain stable in TE buffer for several months. Contaminating RNA can be eliminated with RNase A (20 ng/µl final concentration) either during or after DNA restriction digestion. ■

Sclerotia of false smut (FSm) of rice from Assam, India

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Sclerotia of FSm *Claviceps oryzae sativae* Hashioka were found in Assam for the first time in late Nov 1991.

Less than 1% of the FSm spore balls in a rainfed lowland winter rice (Jul-Dec) crop had the sclerotia. They were borne as peelings from the surface of some spore balls and looked like petals of a flower bud (Fig. 1). Two sclerotia usually developed on a spore ball. They were never formed inside the spore balls.

Sclerotia were shed easily and were collected from the ground near rice hills. The largest sclerotium measured 14 × 7 mm, the smallest was 5 × 3 mm (Fig. 2).

The maximum and minimum temperatures during the week in which sclerotia developed ranged from 20 to 26 °C and from 11 to 15 °C, respectively. The relatively low temperatures during late Nov to early Dec induced sclerotia formation.

The sclerotia germinated after 3 mo when buried in sterile moist sand. They produced stalked stroma with plenty of ascospores.

FSm sclerotia were earlier reported in India at altitudes of 1,200 m and above in the hilly regions of the north where

1. Sclerotia of FSm borne on spore ball.

2. Sclerotia of FSm detached from spore ball.

temperate climate prevails. The sclerotia recently observed are in the plains region (Jorhat) at an altitude of 91 m. Sclerotia, through ascospores, can cause primary infection of rice. ■

A rapid method for DNA fingerprinting of the rice blast fungus *Pyricularia grisea*

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DNA fingerprinting and phylogenetic analysis based on the repetitive DNA probe MGR586 (Dupont) have been useful in studying the population structure of the rice blast fungus *P. grisea*. The DNA fingerprints are used to group isolates according to genetic similarity. The inference is that the groups share a common ancestor and,

Association between groups of isolates defined by RAPD (primer J-06) and RFLP (probe MGR586).^a

RFLP (MGR586)	RAPD (J-06)	Isolates (no.)
1, 1c, 1d, 1e	1	24
7, 7a	2	12
4, 4a, 4b, 4c	3, 4, 5	69
2	6	1
3	7	5
9	8	1
11	9	1
14	10	5
10	11	1
13	12	1

^aMGR586 designations with the same number and different letters are very similar but not identical (80% of bands in common). Each distinct profile produced by RAPD (J-06) was given a different number. Designations for groups of isolates are arbitrary.